

AVALIAÇÃO DA HABILIDADE DE CRESCIMENTO DE *ARTHROSPIRA* SP. EM SAIS DE METÁIS PESADOS E SEU EFEITO EM ALGUNS COMPONENTES CELULARESEVALUATION OF *ARTHROSPIRA* SP. GROWTH ABILITY ON HEAVY METAL SALTS AND THEIR EFFECT ON SOME CELLULAR COMPONENTSتقييم قدرة نمو جنس *Arthrospira* على املاح المعادن الثقيلة وتأثيرها على بعض المكونات الخلويةHiba Khaleel Saeed Al-Shakarchi^{1*} and Yousef Jabbar Al-Shahery²¹Department of Biophysics, College of Science, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq.²Department of Biology, College of Education for Pure Science, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq.

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RESUMO

Arthrospira sp. é um microorganismo aquático e fotossintético amplamente empregado como complemento alimentar, devido ao seu rico conteúdo de nutrientes, proteínas e carboidratos. Neste estudo, uma cepa local de cianobactéria do gênero *Arthrospira* foi isolada do solo iraquiano, na região da cidade de Mosul, usando o Meio No. 10 de Chu. A taxa de crescimento, bem como os efeitos sobre a biomassa e o conteúdo de componentes celulares das proteínas, carboidratos e clorofila dessa cepa, foram avaliadas apenas no meio de melação ou suplementadas com sais de ferro, cobre, níquel, cádmio e cobalto após quinze dias de incubação. Os resultados mostraram que a melhor taxa de crescimento (1,09 OD), o maior valor de biomassa (120,0 mg / l), teor de proteínas (297,2 mg / l), teor de clorofila (14,9 mg / l) e teor de carboidratos (400,0 mg / l) de *Arthrospira* sp. foi alcançado após quinze dias de incubação. Foi observado que a adição de sais de ferro, cobre, níquel, cádmio e cobalto ao melação aumentou o conteúdo de biomassa, proteínas e carboidratos de *Arthrospira* sp. Observou-se que a maior concentração de biomassa (1960 mg/l) foi obtido quando *Arthrospira* sp. cultivadas em melação suplementado com níquel. Além disso, nenhum dos sais metálicos adicionados ao meio de melação aumentou o teor de proteína de *Arthrospira* sp. Por outro lado, a adição de cobre, níquel e cobalto ao meio mostrou um efeito adverso no teor de proteína. Foi demonstrado que a adição de sais de ferro no meio do melação aumentou os carboidratos e o teor de clorofila de *Arthrospira* sp. Esses resultados sugerem que *Arthrospira* sp. pode ser utilizado para a biorremediação da poluição por metais pesados no ambiente e nas instalações industriais.

Palavras-chave: *Arthrospira*, cianobactéria, melação, sais de metais pesados, poluentes.

ABSTRACT

Arthrospira sp. is an aquatic and photosynthetic microorganism that is extensively employed as a food supplement due to its rich contents of nutrients, proteins, and carbohydrates. In this study, a local strain of cyanobacterium of the genus *Arthrospira* was isolated from the Iraqi soil, in the region of Mosul city, using the Chu's Medium No. 10. The growth rate, as well as the effects on biomass and cellular component contents of proteins, carbohydrates, and chlorophyll of this strain, were evaluated on the molasses medium alone or supplemented with iron, copper, nickel, cadmium and cobalt salts after fifteen days of incubation. The results showed that the best growth rate (1.09 OD), the highest value of biomass (120.0 mg/l), proteins content (297.2 mg/l), chlorophyll content (14.9 mg/l) and carbohydrates content (400.0 mg/l) of *Arthrospira* sp. was achieved after fifteen days of incubation. Generally, it was observed that adding iron, copper, nickel, cadmium, and cobalt salts into the molasses medium increased the contents of biomass, proteins, and carbohydrates of *Arthrospira* sp.. It was noticed that the highest biomass concentration (1960 mg/l) was obtained when *Arthrospira* sp. grown on molasses medium supplemented with nickel. Also, none of the metal salts added to the molasses medium increased the protein content of *Arthrospira* sp.. Conversely, adding copper, nickel, and cobalt to the medium showed an adverse effect on the protein content. It was shown that adding iron metal salts into the molasses medium increased the carbohydrates and the chlorophyll contents of *Arthrospira* sp.. These results suggest that

Arthrospira sp. can be utilized for the bioremediation of heavy metals pollution in the environment and industrial sites.

Keywords: *Arthrospira*, cyanobacterium, molasses medium, Heavy Metal Salts, Pollutants.

المخلص

يعتبر جنس *Arthrospira* من الكائنات الحية الدقيقة المائية والقادرة على التمثيل الضوئي والتي تستخدم على نطاق واسع كمكملات غذائية بسبب محتوياتها الغنية من المواد الغذائية والبروتينات والكربوهيدرات. في هذه الدراسة، تم عزل سلالة محلية من البكتيريا الخضراء المزرقة للجنس *Arthrospira* من تربة عراقية في مدينة الموصل باستخدام الوسط Chu رقم 10. تم تقييم معدل النمو، وكذلك التأثير على محتويات الكتلة الحيوية والمكونات الخلوية من البروتينات والكربوهيدرات والكلوروفيل على هذه السلالة، على وسط دبس السكر وحده أو بعد إضافة أملاح المعادن التالية الحديد، النحاس، النيكل، الكاديوم، والكوبالت بعد خمسة عشر يوماً من الحضنة. أظهرت النتائج أن أفضل معدل نمو (1.09 كثافة ضوئية)، أعلى قيمة للكتلة الحيوية (120.0 ملغم / لتر)، محتوى البروتينات (297.2 ملغم / لتر)، محتوى الكلوروفيل (14.9 ملغم / لتر) ومحتوى الكربوهيدرات (400.0 ملغم / لتر) لجنس *Arthrospira* تم تحقيقه بعد خمسة عشر يوماً من الحضنة. عموماً، لوحظ أن إضافة أملاح معادن الحديد، النحاس، النيكل، الكاديوم، والكوبالت في وسط الدبس تزيد من محتويات الكتلة الحيوية والبروتينات والكربوهيدرات لجنس *Arthrospira*. لوحظ أنه تم الحصول على أعلى تركيز للكتلة الحيوية (1960 مجم / لتر) عند تنمية جنس *Arthrospira* على دبس السكر المضاف إليه النيكل. بالإضافة إلى أن أي من الأملاح المعدنية المضافة إلى وسط الدبس لم تزيد من محتوى البروتين لجنس *Arthrospira*. وعلى العكس، فإن إضافة النحاس والنيكل والكوبالت إلى الوسط أظهرت تأثيراً سلبياً على محتوى البروتين. وقد تبين أن إضافة أملاح معدن الحديد في وسط دبس السكر زاد من محتوى الكربوهيدرات والكلوروفيل لجنس *Arthrospira*. تشير النتائج إلى أن بالإمكان استخدام جنس *Arthrospira* في المعالجة البيولوجية للتلوث بالمعادن الثقيلة في البيئة والمواقع الصناعية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: *Arthrospira*، البكتيريا الخضراء المزرقة، وسط دبس السكر، أملاح المعادن الثقيلة، الملوثات.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cyanobacteria are a broad group of organisms that were previously included with algae in the classification of the plant kingdom. Currently, they fall within the group of negative eubacteria to Gram stain (Kozhevnikov and Kozhevnikova 2011). Cyanobacteria are the cause of damage to the aquatic environment or to the lives of aquatic life, or even to human life. They are one of the dangerous, polluting sources to the water, especially the liquefaction water, through releasing of many toxins, and this leads to harm to the lives of millions of people on the globe (Cabral, 2010). In addition, they threaten the aquatic organisms in their environments such as fish and invertebrates, and thus they affect the lives of humans and even animals that feed on these aquatic organisms (Schirmermeister *et al.*, 2011).

On the other hand, cyanobacteria have countless benefits. Many of them are sources for the production of economically essential materials, which encourage their cultivation and the production of biomass. Cyanobacteria are tremendous sources of many organic acids, cosmetics, enzymes, monosaccharides, and polysaccharides, and are also sources of many pharmaceutical and industrial materials (Markou *et al.*, 2012). Cyanobacteria are able to convert their mode of nutrition from autotrophic to saprophytic. This unique characteristic enables these organisms to take advantage of utilizing the carbon sources available in the nutritional

medium to produce biomass. Therefore, the production of this biomass can then be exploited economically for different purposes and at the same time to remove different pollutants resulting from various industrial activities such as sugar production factories, tanning plants and meat productions (Habib *et al.*, 2008).

In recent years, cyanobacteria have been utilized to get rid of the toxic effects of industrial waste residues containing toxic materials such as heavy metals. Cyanobacteria have various mechanisms in response to the toxic effects of these substances, and their resistance mechanisms are different according to the type of cyanobacterial strain and the type of pollutant (Rathinam *et al.*, 2010). Some cyanobacteria showed their ability to secrete extracellular compounds that have the potential to bind to heavy metals. Heavy metals and ions have the ability to combine with functional groups that are found in bioactive molecules such as OH, NH₄, COOH, PO₄, and SH, and convert them into forms that cannot enter the living cells, or reduce the effectiveness of the ions by controlling the permeability of the cell membranes (Pereira *et al.*, 2011).

These mechanisms, which cyanobacteria use to resist the toxic effect of minerals or prevent them from entering the cell, are known as exclusion. Moreover, many cyanobacterial strains have the ability to remove the toxic effect inside their cells by forming peptide compounds that are rich in SH. In the case of exposure to high concentrations of minerals or when exposed to

sub-lethal concentrations, they lead to the production of peptide compounds that are rich in GSH (Rastogi *et al.*, 2015). In both cases, these compounds are called Phyto-chelating compounds, which are rich in cysteine amino acid.

Cyanobacteria possess a large number of genera and species that can be exploited to be used as ion metals bioremediation agents due to their ability to accumulation ion metals in their bodies (Godlewska *et al.*, 2019). However, since there were limited studies about bacteria from the local environments of Mosul city (Al-Qatan *et al.*, 2019), so, this study aimed to isolate a pure local strain of the genus *Arthrospira* and to study its ability to utilize the molasses as a medium of growth and to evaluate adding some heavy metals on some cellular components of *Arthrospira* sp.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Materials and Methods for this study as shown below in paragraphs:

1. Isolation and cultivation of *Arthrospira* sp.

Soil samples were collected from the local environment of Mosul city (Iraq); soil sample was mixed, and a suspension of 1 g (dry weight equivalent) in 10 ml of sterile water was prepared (Prasanna, 2017). One ml of the soil suspension was then diluted serially (three-fold) and used in the isolation of the bacteria by standard spread-plate dilution method described by (Seeley *et al.*, 1970; Banoon and Ali, 2018). Each diluted cultured was poured on Chu's Medium No. 10 agar and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C, light 2500 Lux for 15 days, or till appear the growth. The Chu's Medium No. 10 was used for the initial isolation of the Cyanobacteria and for the purification and the cultivation of *Arthrospira* sp. The medium was prepared according to (Chu, 1942) by weighting (40 g calcium nitrate, 25 g magnesium sulfate, 5 g dipotassium phosphate, 20 g sodium carbonate, 25 g sodium silicate, and 8 g iron chloride) (BDH, UK) and 10% Agar-Agar (Himedia, India). The components were dissolved in one L (final volume) of distilled water (reagent water type IV, ASTM D1193), and the pH adjusted to 7.6-7.8, then sterilize by autoclaving at 15 lbs pressure (121 °C) for 15 minutes (Aryal, 2015). After fifteen days (appearance of the growth); One colony was picked from agar plates then cultured on Chu10 agar and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C, light 2500 Lux for 15 days for purification, the subcultured on the Chu10 solid agar was

repeated several times to obtain a pure representative colony according to shape of colony, appearance and microscopic examination using compound Microscope (Olympus Cx21, Germany). Then a pure colony of the *Arthrospira* sp. was picked up and cultured in 10 ml of Chu broth media at 28 ± 1 °C, light (250 lux) at 100 rpm for 15 days for obtaining the *Arthrospira* sp. inoculum, which is used in subsequent experiments.

2. Preparation the Molasses medium

The culture media was distilled water (reagent water type IV), plus 20% (v/v) Zarrouk's medium (Zarrouk, 1966). Each component of the Zarrouk medium was sterilized separately by autoclaving at 121 °C for 15 min. After cooling, the solutions were mixed, and the medium was supplemented with $0.75 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of concentrated molasses (Table 1) that obtained from the Iraqi sugar industry at Mosul city, this medium was divided into 95 ml for each flask and inoculated with 5 ml of Chu 10 broth medium containing the *Arthrospira* sp. To study the growth ability of *Arthrospira* sp. in the molasses medium with heavy metals salts and to study their effects on some cellular components, different gradual concentrations (mg/l) of the following heavy metal salts; iron chloride ($\text{FeCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), copper chloride ($\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), nickel chloride ($\text{NiCl}_2\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), cadmium chloride (CdCl_2) and cobalt (CoCl_2) were prepared and added to the medium and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C, light 2500 Lux for fifteen days.

3. Analysis Methods

The *Arthrospira* sp. biomass concentration was daily determined by measuring the optical density using spectrophotometry (Labomed Inc, USA), where 1 ml of the culture medium was taken for measuring at ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 670 \text{ nm}$) (Costa *et al.*, 2002). The pH of the cultures was measured every two days using a digital pH meter (Sartorius, Germany) (Schmidell *et al.*, 2001). The carbohydrates content (mg/L) was estimated by the "phenol-sulfuric acid" method (Dubois *et al.*, 1951) By taking (10) ml of the culture and then mixing by an ultrasonic homogenizer (Sonic Ruptor 400, USA). Then the mixed culture was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for ten minutes after centrifuging 1 ml of the supernatant, one ml of phenol solution (5%), and 5 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid were added. The mixture was then vortexed and incubated in a water bath for 30

minutes, measured by spectrophotometry at 477 nm, and then carbohydrate concentrations were calculated in the samples based on the standard curve using glucose. The Mackinney (1941) method was used to estimate the total chlorophyll content by taking five ml of the culture and pelleted by centrifuging at 3500 rpm for two minutes. The pellet was homogenized with 5 ml of 80% of acetone and incubated in a water bath at 70 °C for 2 minutes. Next, it was centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 5 minutes, and the clear supernatant was taken and read at 665 nm in a spectrophotometer (Labomed Inc, USA) against acetone as blank. The chlorophyll content was calculated using Equation 1.

Chlorophyll content = optical density at 665 nm × 13.9 (Eq. 1)

(13.9 is a constant derived from the absorption coefficient). The protein content of *Arthrospira sp.* was estimated according to the Lowry method, most widely used to estimate the amount of proteins (Lowry *et al.* 1951).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

From the results, it was found that *Arthrospira sp.* contains multicellular cylindrical trichomes with a blue-green color (Figure 1). However, these characterizations are typical morphology for the genus *Arthrospira* that were described by Tomaselli *et al.*, 1996.

3.1. Effect of different incubation periods

This experiment was designed to see the ability of *Arthrospira sp.* to exploit the byproduct of molasses to grow *Arthrospira sp.* as a liquid nutritional medium during different incubation times. The results showed that the best growth (1.09 OD) of *Arthrospira sp.* was achieved after fifteen days of incubation (Table 2). Additionally, the highest value of biomass (120.0 mg/l), the highest proteins content (297.2 mg/l), the highest chlorophyll content (14.9 mg/l) and the highest carbohydrates content (400.0 mg/l) were recorded at the same incubation period at the final pH (8.92). These results confirmed that the best growth of the studied species achieves the best protein, chlorophyll, and carbohydrate content as well as possessing the best biomass and higher pH value.

3.2. Effect of heavy metal salts

The growth rate, biomass, protein content, chlorophyll content, and carbohydrates content were evaluated after fifteen days of incubation in molasses medium without and with supplements of different metals salts. From the results, it was observed that adding metal salts into molasses has a variable effect on the growth rate (Figure 2), biomass, and cell components of *Arthrospira sp.* (Figure 3). In general, concentrations of biomass, protein content, and carbohydrates content were increased by adding the metal salts into the molasses medium.

The highest biomass concentration (1960 mg/l) was obtained when *Arthrospira sp.* grown on molasses medium supplemented with nickel chloride (Figure 4). Similarly, adding cadmium, copper, cobalt, and iron chloride into molasses medium were also increased the biomass concentrations of *Arthrospira sp.* To 1801 mg/l, 1734 mg/l, 1640 mg/l and 1626 mg/l accordingly. Although metals induce biosynthesis of some compounds by cyanobacterial strains, they may also have detrimental effects in high concentrations. Nickel plays an important role in many metabolic activities of cyanobacteria. Nickel is directly coordinated by proteins (Ragsdale, 2009) or through the tetrapyrrole ring of coenzyme F₄₃₀, which coordinates a nickel atom in methyl-coenzyme M reductase (MCR); MCR is a nickel tetrahydrocorphinoid (coenzyme F₄₃₀) containing enzyme concerned in the biological synthesis and anaerobic oxidation of methane. MCR catalyzes the conversion of methyl-2-mercaptoethanesulfonate (methyl-SCoM) and N-7-mercaptoheptanoylthreonine phosphate (CoB₇SH) to CH₄ and the corresponding heterodisulfide (CoBS-SCoM) (Wongnate and Ragsdale, 2015; Scheller *et al.*, 2013; Kobayashi and Shimizu 1999). Nickel serves as a cofactor in an enzyme urease, which is needed to use urea as a nitrogen source (Oliveira and Antia, 1984; Collier *et al.*, 1999; Miazek *et al.*, 2015). Studies have shown that metals, such as cadmium, copper and cobalt, at low concentrations had a stimulatory effect on growth of cyanobacteria (Mann *et al.*, 2002; Shanab *et al.*, 2012; Dupont *et al.*, 2012; Twining and Baines, 2013) and these are consistent with the results obtained in the present study.

On the other hand, the addition of iron and cadmium metals had no effect on increasing the protein content of *Arthrospira sp.* as the concentrations were almost similar (Figure 5). It was also noticed that copper and cadmium had the most negative effect on proteins and carbohydrates contents compared with molasses

medium alone as the concentrations were 85 mg/l and 243 mg/l accordingly (Figure 5 and 6). Copper is a metal necessary for the proper growth and development of plants (Sunda, 1989). It is an essential microelement for cyanobacteria because it is an integral component of plastocyanin in the photosynthetic electron-transport chain. However, high concentrations of copper are effective as a cyanocide and are usually used for removing undesired cyanobacterial growth in water reservoirs and drainage systems (Surosz and Palinska, 2004). On the other hand, cadmium is known to be one of the most hazardous rare metals in the environment because of its high toxicity to all components of aquatic communities (Vymazal, 1987) and has received widespread of attention because of its accelerated release into the environment as the result of industrial pollution (Surosz and Palinska 2004; Wieczorek *et al.*, 2018).

It was shown that adding iron and nickel metals into molasses medium increased the carbohydrates content of *Arthrospira* sp. from 400 mg/l in molasses medium to 557 and 463 mg/l (Figure 6) accordingly. However, it is well known that iron is an essential metal for most organisms, including cyanobacteria (Zhang *et al.*, 2018). Iron is involved in the biosynthesis of chlorophyll and phycobilin pigments, electron transport reactions, and inorganic nitrate assimilation (Greene *et al.* 1992; Li *et al.*, 2016). This is very obvious in the present results as the chlorophyll content was higher in the molasses medium supplemented with iron chloride (Figure 3). Our findings were agreed with other studies about the effect the industrial pollutants on the efficacy of cyanobacteria (Abdel-Raouf *et al.*, 2012). However, the heavy metals resistance genes for this exotic strain need to be sequenced or RAPD-typing or detect the resistance genes for further studies as recommended by Salih and Shafeek, 2019; Banoon *et al.*, 2019; Aziz *et al.*, 2019).

4. CONCLUSIONS:

This work has demonstrated that the *Arthrospira* sp. isolated from the Iraqi environment, in the region of Mosul city was able to grow on the byproducts of industrial sugar waste (molasses) alone or supplemented with heavy metals. In this study, it was observed that the addition of iron, copper, nickel, cadmium, and cobalt metals into the molasses medium increased the biomass content. Moreover, while adding iron and nickel metals into the molasses

medium increased the carbohydrates content of *Arthrospira* sp., adding copper, nickel, and cobalt decreased the protein content of *Arthrospira* sp. compared to the molasses medium. This study suggested that this local strain of cyanobacteria can be used as a reliable biological system for bioremediation of heavy metals pollution in the environment.

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Table 1: Approximate Component of chemical analysis of molasses medium according to Clarke (2003)

Main constituents	Components	Normal range
water		17-25%
Sugars	Sucrose	30-40%
	Glucose (dextrose)	4-9%
	Fructose (levulose)	5-12%
	Other reducing substances (as invert)	1-4%
	Total reducing substances (as invert)	10-25%
Other carbohydrates	Gums, starch, pentosans, also traces of hexitols; myoinositol, d-mannitol, and uronic acids.	2-5%
Ash	As carbonates	7-15%
	Bases: Potassium oxide (30–50%), Calcium oxide (7–15%), Magnesium oxide (2–14%), Sodium oxide (0.3–9%), Metal oxides (as ferric) (0.4–2.7%) Acids: Sulfur trioxide (7–27%), Chloride (12–20%), Phosphorus pentoxide (0.5–2.5%), Silicates and insolubles (1–7%)	
Nitrogenous compounds	Crude protein (as N × 6.25)	2.5-4.5%
	True protein	0.5-1.5%
	Amino acids, principally aspartic and glutamic acids, including some pyrrolidine carboxylic acids	0.3-0.5%
	Unidentified nitrogenous compounds	1.5-3.0%
Nonnitrogenous	Aconitic acid (1–5%), citric, malic, oxalic, glycolic	1.5-6.0%
	Mesaconic, succinic, fumaric, tartaric	0.5-1.5%
Wax, sterols, and phosphatides		0.1-1.0%
Vitamins	Thiamin (B ₁)	2-10 ppm
	Riboflavin (B ₂)	1-6 ppm
	Pyridoxine (B ₆)	1-10 ppm
	Nicotinamide	1-25 ppm
	Pantothenic acid	2.25 ppm
	Folic acid	10-50 ppm
	Biotin	0.1-2 ppm

Table 2: Effect of incubation periods on the growth rate, biomass, proteins, chlorophyll, and carbohydrates contents of *Arthrospira* sp.

Incubation period (days)	Final pH	Growth rate (OD)	Biomass mg/l	Proteins content mg/l	Chlorophyll content mg/l	Carbohydrates content mg/l
3	7.71	0.21	211.0	80.0	7.3	103.0
5	7.72	0.32	332.0	82.3	9.6	183.0
7	7.90	0.49	389.0	89.0	11.3	199.0
9	8.01	0.65	401.0	122.0	11.9	256.0
11	8.09	0.77	539.0	189.2	12.7	301.0
13	8.33	0.99	805.0	238.3	12.9	360.0
15	8.92	1.09	120.0	297.2	14.9	400.0
17	8.80	0.89	109.0	223.0	13.6	323.0

Figure 1: Light microscopy (magnification 10X) of *Arthrospira* sp. from the Chu's No. 10 agar medium (left) and from the Chu's No. 10 broth medium (right).

Figure 2: Growth rate of *Arthrospira* sp. grown on molasses medium alone or supplemented with different metals after fifteen days of incubation.

Figure 3: Biomass, protein content, chlorophyll content, and carbohydrates content of *Arthrospira* sp. grown on molasses medium alone or supplemented with different metals after fifteen days of incubation.

Figure 4: Biomass concentration of *Arthrospira sp.* grown on molasses medium alone or supplemented with iron, copper, nickel, cadmium, and cobalt chloride, respectively, after fifteen days of incubation.

Figure 5: Proteins content of *Arthrospira sp.* grown on molasses medium alone or supplemented with iron, copper, nickel, cadmium, and cobalt chloride, respectively, after fifteen days of incubation.

Figure 6: Carbohydrates content of *Arthrospira* sp. grown on molasses medium alone or supplemented with iron, copper, nickel, cadmium, and cobalt chloride, respectively, after fifteen days of incubation.